

Elements of Strategic National Defense in the State Maritime Indonesia

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Abstract: *National Defense is an element important in a country that is related to the protection to all citizens, region and the political system in it in countering various threats. National defense is considered very important for all countries, including Indonesia. For the author, the implementation of the National Defense Strategy is carried out by mobilizing all national resources after going through a transformation process to change the potential of national resources (ideology, politics, economy, socio-culture, military, geography, demography and natural resources) into elements of national power (Elements of national power). As an archipelagic country with 80% of the sea area and 20% of the land area, the threat to Indonesia's sovereignty and territory lies at sea. These conditions make Indonesia vulnerable to threats. Therefore, in dealing with these threats, are needed elements of national power. The elements of national power consist of several elements, namely non-military power and military power.*

Keywords: Elements of National Power, National Defense, Strategy Maritime

I. INTRODUCTION

National Defense is the principal element of a country because it involves the interests of a state in protecting citizens, regions and political systems of various threats from other countries. This is in line with the opinion of KJ Holsti, namely that in defense, it is the National Interest which is considered as a core value or something that is considered the most vital for the country and concerns the existence of a country [1].

National Defense Policies and Strategies are formulated through several basic considerations in accordance with national goals and interests. The national defense policy refers to the Government's Vision and Mission which is realized in a proportional, balanced and coordinated manner. To realize the vision and mission of the government towards the development of national defense that covers objectives, strategic goals, how to achieve the goals and defense resources in order to realize the power and the country's defense capability is powerful, effective and powerful deterrence. high

National Defense organized through a strategy, in order to achieve strategic goals and objectives set. The strategy is formulated in 3 basic substances which include: what is maintained, how to maintain and with what to maintain, which is described through the form of goals and objectives, how to achieve the goals and the resources used. In the State of Indonesia, the implementation of a universal defense strategy refers to the development of a national defense system that is built on a priority scale through efforts such as: increasing the professionalism of the Indonesian National Army (TNI), Preparation and development of people's power, as well as the development of defense technology in supporting the availability of Alutsista [2].

As Indonesia's world maritime axis in achieving the goal of a strong and resilient national defense, it requires the ability to think strategically and be historically motivated. Think and develop what elements are contained in the Strategic Science of National Defense in order to develop tasks in the future.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the work of this writing, the author uses a literature review as a suitable writing technique. Literature Review is a writing technique by collecting data related to things or variables in the form of books, transcripts, notes, magazines, newspapers, inscriptions, agendas, meeting minutes and so on. The author chooses to conduct a study

through documentation because it can strengthen the existing data and evidence and can complement the research results from a more accurate and reliable literature review [3].

III. LITERATUR REVIEW

A. Elements Strategic of National Power

Rich countries will not be considered as strong countries if they are weak in political strategy and policies as well as when the country has good policies but is not supported by a strong economy [4]. The defense strategic framework is very important for a country because it is closely related to national power. According to Morgenthau, national power is the ability of a country to influence and control other countries (to influence and control) so that the country does something the country wants "Anything that establishes and maintains control of man over man" [5].

National power can be divided into three, soft power, hard power, and smart power. Soft power is the ability of a country to persuade other actors (to persuade) and also influence the policies of other countries. These forces are strongly influenced by economic, technological, ideological and state positions in international relations. Countries that have this position are very domains in the international community, of course they have strong soft power and whatever policies are taken will affect other countries either directly or indirectly.

Meanwhile, hard power is the ability of other countries to impose their will on other countries through armed force and economic influence, even both. The difference between the concepts of soft power and hard power lies in their efforts and actions to influence other countries. Where soft power makes efforts to be persuasive while hard power makes efforts to coercively that is coercive [6]. And lastly, smart power is a combination of classic power (hard power) with modern power (soft power). Smart power tends to be directed at the ability of a country to develop strategies and tactics in an effort to achieve the country's interests [7].

Hans J. Morgenthau (1990) said that there are 9 main elements in describing the elements of national power, namely elements of geography, natural resources, industrial capability, military strength, population, national character, national morale, diplomacy quality and government quality. The 9 elements are the main source of the strength of a country [8]. In classical theory, the sources of state power cover three major aspects, namely natural sources, socio-psychological aspects, and synthetic or artificial aspects. Aspects of natural sources include the geographical elements of the country, the availability of natural resources, and the human population. Socio-psychological aspects include state stability, quality of government or leadership and political will. The last is the synthetic aspect which includes military strength and industrial quality.

Conventional methods describe the geographical strength of a country can be measured through the size of the country's territory. Resources are measured through the availability of food, oil and energy. Population quality through population and reading ability. Industrial strength is measured by GDP or exports/imports, military strength through the number of troops and the quality of weapons. Political will is measured by the level of determination/ability of the government. Stability is measured by whether or not the condition of a country is stable. And the last Leadership is measured through the strength or weakness of the country's leadership [9].

B. Indonesian Defense Strategic Framework

The national defense strategy is formulated with several underlying considerations. In the State of Indonesia, the national defense strategy is formulated in accordance with the understanding and views of the Indonesian people. This view is contained in 3 basic substances, namely proportional, balanced and coordinated. In this strategy, of course, it is carried out by formulating goals, strategic targets, methods and means used to realize defense forces and capabilities that are responsible and have high deterrence.

The National Defense Strategy is compiled by considering 3 basic elements, namely to shape, to respond, and to prepare. to shape, namely a strategy that is able to create and shape a national and international security environment that can guarantee national interests by promoting regional stability, reducing and eliminating threats, preventing conflicts, and preventing aggression and other acts of violence. Second, to respond, namely a strategy that is able to respond to various spectrums of crises that can create threats and risks to the national interest. Third, to prepare, namely a strategy that is able to prepare a defense to face an uncertain future by focusing on efforts to build strength, develop concepts, and organize defense that utilizes technological advances to protect national interests. [10]

The National Defense Strategy is formulated with 3 basic substances, namely end, means and ways. The objectives to be achieved are to maintain and protect the sovereignty of the state, the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and to protect the safety of the entire nation which is translated into 4 strategic objectives (ends). Second, what resources will be used to maintain and achieve the goals and objectives to be achieved (means), by deploying military defense that is integrated and synergized with non-military defense. Third, how the resources used to achieve the goals and objectives are maintained (ways), namely by planning, preparing, and implementing a strong and highly deterrent state defense system in accordance with the Indonesian people regarding war and peace. This method is realized by compiling an active defensive defense that is universal and arranged in layers supported by the ability to participate in realizing world peace and the independence of a strong and independent defense industry as well as by mobilizing elements of national power in a synergistic and integrated manner [11].

The National Defense Strategy is implemented by mobilizing all national resources. To support the implementation of the National Defense Strategy, all national resources are mobilized after going through a transformation process to transform the potential of national resources (ideology, politics, economy, socio-culture, military, geography, demography and natural resources) into elements of national power (elements of national power).

Elements in the strategic aspect include geographic character, being close to the sea, having a relatively long beach, the character of a nation that considers the sea as an important asset to improve national welfare, natural resources that support maritime power, and the character of a government that has a domain-oriented mindset. Meanwhile, the operational aspect usually consists of three major elements, namely, security forces or in technical terms fighting instruments to protect assets and interests, commercial fleets, and the last is related to industry and services that are able to support both operational elements covering various activities related to sea. Therefore, a strong naval fleet must be built to defend Indonesia, which is geographically an archipelagic country.

C. Indonesian Maritime Strategic Elements

Indonesia is a strategic area that stretches from Sabang to Merauke by having 2 sides of the world cross, namely between 2 continents (Asia and Australia) and between 2 oceans (Indian Ocean and Pacific Ocean). The total island owned by Indonesia is 17,499 with an area of the country of Indonesia is currently approximately 7.81 million km². Indonesia's geographical condition is dominated by an ocean area of 3.25 million KM² and an exclusive economic zone of 2.55 million KM² compared to land which is only about 2.01 million KM² and has maritime borders with 10 (ten) neighboring countries [12]. This makes Indonesia's position as the intersection of various interests of other parties/countries, so that a strong marine defense capability becomes a necessity to uphold national sovereignty from various emerging threats. It can be seen from the explanation above that Indonesia's geographical condition is dominated by the ocean, so it is very closely related to maritime security threats, so a maritime strategy is needed.

The Indonesian Maritime Strategic Element is closely related to maritime security. Maritime security is security that is part of national security, which in implementing national security influences maritime security practices and policies. Maritime security is a more preventive and responsive combination of security that is measured to protect all elements. Maritime strategy is an art that is carried out by directing maritime assets to achieve the desired political goals or objectives. The country's political, economic, and technological environment has a direct relationship to a country's maritime strategy [13]. In the maritime strategy, the sea is the main land in its utilization, and as much as possible it refuses benefits for other countries to take advantage of the maritime wealth of the maritime country.

Christian Bueger's opinion, there are 4 security concepts in maritime security, namely Sea Power, Marine safety, Blue Economy, and Human Security. The concept of Sea Power is the role of all components of national maritime power together with other maritime powers to protect the sustainability of the country, protect sea transportation routes for trade and economic development. Marine safety is the safety of ships and marine institutions with the main objective of protecting professionals and the marine environment. Blue economy is the development of the sea in the economic field where the sea plays an important role in trade and fisheries. The sea has very important natural resources, such as oil and minerals that come from the seabed in the ocean. The development of coastal tourism is also a high economic income, and the last is the concept of human security related to maritime security which contains elements of the availability of food, the availability of shelter, sustainable living, and the availability of safe job vacancies [14].

Maritime Security contains five elements, namely the National Interest (Sovereignty & Legal Aspects) at sea, Safe and peaceful use of the sea, Law enforcement that is not only limited by physical territorial boundaries, Indonesia's active role in maintaining regional security and the need for cooperation between the nation's components. The Maritime Security Approach has 3 (three) basic elements, namely: Awareness of threats and vulnerabilities, Prevention and protection from threats, and Response to potential attacks. Aspects that support Maritime development, Aspects of social and cultural life, Economic aspects, Defense and security aspects, and Science and technology.

Indonesia as an archipelagic country with a total percentage of 80% of the sea area and 20% of the land area, is a threat to Indonesia's sovereignty and territory which is located near the sea. The current threat is getting higher because of Indonesia's geographical position which is in the world trade traffic lane. Every day hundreds and even thousands of merchant and military ships pass through Indonesian waters through four SLOCs. The current state of maritime threats is searobbery and piracy, illegal fishing, transnational threats, illicit trafficking in weapons of mass destruction and related materials, territorial violations, traffic at sea related to separatist movements and the very possible threat of maritime terrorism. It is also estimated that the threat will increase as measured by the intensity, the use of advanced technology, and the development of the mode of operation.

To deal with this threat, elements of national power are needed. Elements of national power consist of elements, namely non-military power and military power. Non-military power which includes ideological power, domestic politics and diplomacy, economy and finance, socio-culture, technology, psychology, information, geography, demography and natural resources. Military power which includes land power, sea power, and air power which is strengthened by reserve and support forces.

Land power is the totality and synergy of real national capabilities and forces on land. Ground forces include the strength of the army, the strength of various units and organizations, mobilization, technology, national industry, land areas, resources and people that can be deployed to influence the battle on land. Ground forces are projected to control the use of land areas for the benefit of war military operations and military operations other than war. Land power cannot be separated from sea power and air power.

Sea power is the totality and synergy of real national capabilities and power at sea. Naval power includes naval power, the strength of various units and organizations, mobilization, technology, national industry, maritime areas, resources and maritime communities that can be deployed to influence combat at sea. Sea power is projected to control the use of the sea area (sea control) for the sake of war military operations and military operations other than war. Sea power is also deployed to control trade and commerce at sea, as well as for the purposes of deterrence, sea denial, defense diplomacy and exerting political influence in peacetime. Sea power can be deployed to help influence battles on land and in the air. Sea power cannot be separated from air power and land power.

Air power is the totality and synergy of real national capabilities and power in the air. Air power includes the power of the air force, the power of various units and organizations, mobilization, technology, national industry, national airspace and the aerospace community that can be deployed to influence combat in the air. Air power is projected to control airspace in the interest of war military operations and military operations other than war. Air power is deployed to help influence battles on land and at sea through air supremacy. Air power cannot be separated from land power and sea power. Air power is also used to support deterrence and defense diplomacy.

Elements of national power are deployed in synergy and grouped into soft power and hard power and smart power to support national defense efforts. The potential of national resources that are transformed into national defense forces are used for the implementation of national defense. National defense resources rely on military defense resources and non-military defense resources.

Referring to the Regulation of the Coordinating Minister for Maritime Affairs and Investment of the Republic of Indonesia No. 6 of 2020 concerning the Strategic Plan of the Coordinating Ministry for Maritime Affairs and Investment for the Year 2020-2024. The Joko Widodo government has made efforts that can be broadly classified into two approaches, namely the hard approach by strengthening the enforcement of maritime defense, security and safety in protecting the territory and marine resources and the soft approach by strengthening the diplomacy and maritime negotiations. These two efforts are to realize Indonesia as the World Maritime Axis.

a. Hard Effort

In a hard effort approach by strengthening the enforcement of maritime defense, security and safety in protecting marine areas and resources, it is necessary to have elements that are divided into three elements. These three elements must be owned sequentially by the Indonesian government in the idea of realizing the World Maritime Axis in order to be able to deal with maritime security issues properly. First, the government must first create a maritime doctrine as the basis for policy making. Furthermore, the government must build Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA) as an insight for every element of the country to work together to support the government. Finally, after these two elements are met, the government can start focusing on building sea power as an instrument in dealing with maritime security issues [15].

b. Soft Effort

The younger generation must be exposed to maritime problems from an early age through education. Thus, there will be a sense of ownership to make Indonesia a maritime country. After making a hard approach (hard effort) such as the realization of maritime doctrine, Maritime Domain Awareness and Sea Power, the Government of Joko Widodo also took a soft effort.

- **Strengthening Maritime Diplomacy Efforts**
Maritime diplomacy is a negotiation or negotiation conducted by two or more countries regarding maritime boundaries, maritime cooperation and defense.
- **Take an active role in ASEAN and IORA and IOM**
Maritime diplomacy carried out by Indonesia in the region integrates two maritime diplomacy approaches. First, diplomatic efforts in the form of soft maritime diplomacy through cooperation and persuasion including implementing cooperation, persuasion, and coercion at the level of countries that are members of ASEAN countries including through the ASEAN Maritime Forum (AMF) and the Expanded ASEAN Maritime Forum (EAMF). a regional organization in the Indian Ocean region called the Indian Ocean Rim Association (IORA) and also through a leading intergovernmental migration field that works closely with government partners, intergovernmental and non-governmental organizations called the International Organization for Migration (IOM)[16].

IV. CONCLUSION

In the implementation of the National Defense Strategy, all national resources are deployed after going through a transformation process to transform the potential of national resources (ideology, politics, economy, socio-culture, military, geography, demography and natural resources) into elements of national power (elements of national defense). national power). Elements in the strategic aspect include geographic character, being close to the sea, having a relatively long beach, the character of a nation that considers the sea as an important asset to improve national welfare, natural resources that support maritime power, and the character of a government that has a domain-oriented mindset. maritime. National strength is an important element in the Strategic Elements of State Defense in the interaction of the global system. The greater the national power of a country, the more likely it is for a country to achieve its national interests because national power is a tool to achieve this. In addition, national power has also experienced a paradigm shift from what initially only focused on hard power aspects, has now entered soft power aspects due to shifts in international politics. National strength is also important for predicting the capabilities of other actors so that they can make the right decisions in taking action and formulating foreign policy.

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